

Literature and Politics in Curriculum Making: Teaching Twentieth Century Russian Literature in India

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The teaching of Russian literature in English translation in India goes back to the 1950s. The endeavour was part of the larger cultural, political and academic dialogue with USSR and Socialism which began, in many cases surreptitiously through veiled references in India in the pre-independence days through the All India Progressive Writers' Association. Post-independence, USSR became a very valuable ally and a role model for the poor but growing nation that India was in the 1950s and 1960s. With the inclusion of socialism as a constitutional value in India, a perpetuation of the cultural exchange between India and Russia seemed to be certain.

But the growth of Russian studies in India did not take place at the desired rapid pace, mostly due to our colonial past. In comparison with other countries, India still faces the colonial deficit in this regard. In his 1969 paper 'Soviet Studies in India', R. Vaidyanath states:

“Many western countries, of which the United States is a notable example, have greatly augmented facilities for teaching academic research in Russian and Soviet affairs in the post-war years. At present there exist, within the United States alone, as many as seventy university departments and research centres devoted to the systematic study of Russia before and after the Revolution of 1917. The rapid strides the U.S.A. has made in these studies in the post war years are evidenced by the fact that, compared to the two hundred and fifty doctoral dissertations on Russia and the Soviet Union submitted in the century between 1850 and 1950, one thousand of them have been completed since that date alone. In comparison, India is languishing far behind despite her traditional interest in the USSR.” (Vaidyanath 145).

The reason behind this academic gap cited by Vaidyanath is of course the British colonial rule in India which keenly promoted Indians in developing a mistrust against the “Russian bogey”. He explains further that “the battle against ‘Bolshevism’ in India was fought on many fronts and in diverse forms. First, strict surveillance was kept on the movement of Indians suspected of having been contaminated with the ‘disease’ of Bolshevism; second, the entire mass media was geared to feeding India anti-Bolshevik propaganda and third, even the universities were prevailed upon to immunize their students and scholars against the influence of Bolshevism. . . Consequently, while other countries such as the United States, Germany, France and the U.K were rapidly developing teaching and research facilities and embarking upon extended programmes for training

a cadre of specialists on Russian and Soviet affairs, India was literally forced to turn her back on the USSR” (Vaidyanath 146-148). This assertion is corroborated by the American scholar of Russian studies, Donald Treadgold in his memoir. He recalls how as a youngster growing up in a small town in Oregon in the second decade of twentieth century, he had never heard of Russians. But already by 1940s, especially during and right after World War II, most distinguished universities in U.S.A were setting up state of art departments of Russian Studies and sending students off, if not to USSR, then to other internationally renowned departments of Russian Studies on ‘exposure trips’. Treadgold himself went from Harvard to Oxford in order “to become the student of Benedict Humphrey Sumner, Warden of All Souls College and the foremost English student of Russia up to that time. I had a seminar on Marxism with G.D.H. Cole, precious conversations with Isaiah (not yet knighted) Berlin, attended lectures by A.J.P. Taylor, became lasting friends with Hugh Seton-Watson, and benefited from Oxford in many other ways.” (Treadgold 116) It is evident from such submissions that although Britain itself was deeply invested in the study of USSR, and was home to top departments and scholars of Soviet Studies, this knowledge was forcibly kept away from Indians. The fear of Communism in a colonized country like India was palpable, specifically in taking decisions related to university syllabi. Soviet literature was particularly barred from entering the syllabi in any form to avoid Communist politics from brewing in British-Indian university campuses. Though translations of several Russian and Soviet literary texts were available in Indian languages during the colonial rule, possession of such books was mostly seen as a seditious act.

A change in this scenario of course occurred after independence. The writings and speeches of Jawaharlal Nehru and Rabindranath Tagore on the USSR left a deep impact on the minds of educated young Indians. Post-independence, a need was felt for more extensive study of USSR in India. In response to the growing need for Russian translators, interpreters and teachers, teaching of Russian language courses started in Delhi University in 1946, in the Allahabad University in 1948 and at the Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay in 1950. More and more Indians, especially in diplomatic services and foreign trade organizations needed to acquire a knowledge of the Russian language. Many advanced and nuanced steps towards consolidation of Russian studies in India were taken with the formation of the Institute of Russian Studies and the Indian School of International Studies. Both these institutes later formed the basic kernel of Jawaharlal Nehru University.

The original deficit due to colonial hegemony with which India started in this field may have been filled to a great extent by various renowned departments and institutes of Russian Studies. But what happens in department teaching Russian literature in translation is a different matter. If one were to focus on English departments in Indian universities teaching part or full courses on Russian literature, a different picture emerges. The lop-sided syllabi of English departments which were suffered by our teachers are well known and documented. These departments well into the late-eighties were carrying the colonial burden of British literature if not with pride, then definitely as a bad habit. The *raison d’etre* for this insistence on British literature to my mind is that English was still not seen, taught, used and understood as an Indian language. While many linguists in India were much ahead in their keen understanding of the

complex, hegemonic, dangerous and even detrimental relationship the growth of English shared with the Indian mother tongues, the literature departments were very slow in decolonising their syllabi. Indian universities such as Jawaharlal Nehru University, Delhi University, Hyderabad Central University and the IITs have been at the forefront of decolonizing humanities syllabi especially since the 1990s. JNU of course deserves a special place in this context. Since its inception in 1978, Centre for Linguistics and English (CLE) focussed on languages and literatures from India and from the margins questioning the validity of Eurocentric discourses which prevailed at that time in the academia. Path-breaking courses on African Literature, Canadian Literature, Translation in India and Indian Poetics were taught for the first time in India in this Centre. All the courses taught in this Centre of JNU sought to shift academic focus towards lesser known and lesser studied literatures and yet, there have not been exclusive courses on Russian literature here as well. With its mandate to “establish such departments or institutions as may be necessary for the study of languages, literature and life of foreign countries with a view to inculcating in the students a world perspective and international understanding” (13), JNU did become instrumental in the growth of Centres with expertise in foreign languages, literatures and cultures. The Institute of Russian Studies was merged with JNU, thus marking a rich beginning for the Centre for Russian Studies. But in terms of teaching Russian literature in English translation JNU is at par with most other universities in India.

A cursory look at current syllabi of a few universities which have been at the forefront as far as approaching literary studies from a contemporary, decolonized and post- colonial position is concerned, one finds one or two nineteenth century Russian novels included at the graduate studies level. The English under-graduates are rarely introduced to Russian literature. Universities within Delhi: Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, Jamia Milia Islamia and University of Delhi teach one Russian text each at MA level. Dostoevsky’s *Notes from Underground* is part of several syllabi. Gogol’s *Dead Souls* is part of the European Comedy paper at University of Delhi. Even *Anna Karenina* is part of several MA English syllabi. At Ambedkar University Delhi, Dostoevsky’s *Crime and Punishment* and *Notes from Underground* have been taught since the beginning of MA in English in 2011. *Anna Karenina* also has been taught to some batches. In my own course on Short Story, I have been teaching short fiction by Turgenev, Gogol, Chekhov and Bunin. While Osip Mandelstam and Isaac Babel make rare appearances in our Modernist poetry courses, a sustained study of the twentieth century Russian literature is not considered as important perhaps as the study of twentieth century Afro-American literature for instance. My intervention in this field is largely inspired by my teachers’ grit at JNU to make unusual choices and justify them with years of research and teaching.

The Twentieth Century Russian Literature course was started at Ambedkar University Delhi in 2015 as part of the MA English syllabus. As a standalone course, it explores Russian literature from 1905 to the 1950s.

This course focuses on literature which represents the myriad political and socio-cultural shifts in Russia across first half of the eventful twentieth

century. Literary and art works related to Russian Modernism, Social Realism and dissident Samizdat writing are examined in this course. An attempt is made to study the changes in the definitions of creativity and art which took place in Russia across changing regimes. Beginning with the aftermath of the Russian Revolution of 1905, the course would meander through a study of poetry, drama, art and fiction around Bolshevik Revolution, the World Wars, the rise and fall of Stalinism and the chaotic period of the Thaw (1950s) to forge an understanding of the complex realities that define issues related to identity, creativity and selfhood in twentieth century Russia. (SCAP 2)

This course is to be followed soon by another course in Contemporary Russian Literature to make this study compact, complete and contemporaneous. But the making of these courses has not been easy. A difficult balance needs to be made between the four major shifts politico-literary constituencies this period presents to us: the Russian avant-garde, the Bolshevik and later, Soviet writers, the Russian émigré poets and authors and the dissident samizdat writers. One runs into a methodological problem on noting that these categories are fluid and these compartments porous. I think that the resistance against teaching such courses in Indian universities stems partly from this problem and partly from the fact that 20th century texts in translation are not as readily available as their 19th century counterparts. While Soviet writings in translation became abundantly available in India after independence, the other writers remained unknown to Indian readers for a long time. Publication of the writings from the other categories mentioned above was curtailed and even prohibited in Soviet Russia. Their works remain alive today due to the efforts of critics, scholars and publishers in Europe who supported the émigré and samizdat literature of Russia. And yet many works were destroyed during the Stalinist searches and the bombings during the World War II. To a large extent, even today, we are dependent on sources outside Russia to study and better our understanding of non-Soviet and anti-Soviet literary works.

Since the focus of Moscow publication houses such as Raduga and Progress was on Soviet writing and translation and dissemination of Soviet ideology, countries like India became flooded with state of art and very economical editions of such books published jointly with Indian publishing companies such as People's Publishing House. "An entire generation of Indians grew up reading Soviet books. Magazines such as Soviet Union, Soviet Life, Sovietland and Misha were widely circulated and literary works of Russian giants such as Lev Tolstoy, Turgenev, Gorky, Dostoevsky alongside Soviet books on economics, agriculture, music and poetry had a strong readership in India. Russian publishing agencies such as FLPH, Progress Publishers, Raduga (Rainbow) Publishers, Novosti Press Agency Publishing House, Mir Publishers etc. distributed and marketed their books in India." (People's Publishing House, New Delhi, *Zikr-e-Dilli*). The fierce marketing of these beautifully produced books ensured a place for not just Soviet literature in Indian imagination but also for 19th century literary giants such as Dostoevsky and Tolstoy. Limited and often dangerously surreptitious circulation of

writings by avant-garde poets, émigré writers and critics of the Soviet regime (especially under Stalin) likewise ensured their complete absence in literary discourse in most of the world.

The West of course, partly due to its curiosity about what happens behind the Iron curtain and partly due to its deep suspicion and fear of Communism, encouraged and indulged in promotion of counter-narratives of Communism about and from Soviet Russia. Their attempts therefore to promote the publication and dissemination of works such as Pasternak's *Doctor Zhivago* and Solzhenitsyn's *Gulag Archipelago* cannot be seen as innocent and selfless. Nevertheless, these attempts to rescue valuable critiques of Soviet regime have certainly provided the world another point of view: that coming from the lived reality in Soviet Russia. As discussed earlier in this paper, the West had a head start over India in their research investment in Russia. Many departments in many universities were entirely dedicated to Russian studies in these countries. Talking about USA alone, Ludmila Isurin surmises:

In U.S. universities, interest in learning Russian as a foreign language has been relatively steady over the last 50 years. The so-called "Sputnik effect" - a surge of interest in the Russian language due to the launch of the first Soviet sputnik in 1957 and, as a result, the shocking revelation that the USSR might become a serious rival - is considered the beginning of a new era, during which Russian language programs were established at major American universities. . . .Regardless of any changes in the political climate and the relationship between the two countries, the U.S. State Department still has the Russian language on the list of languages critical to the country's national security (Isurin 25)

So the position from where Russia is seen by United States is that of a rival, a threat and therefore a necessary subject of study. Russia is the constant, dangerous other and the average American response to the representations of this other fall in line with this view. Peter Huidekoper, Jr., an American teacher of Russian literature recalls the reaction of a student after reading *One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich*: "The idea that there could be a relationship of such importance between art and politics, the discovery that poets have been sent to labor camps, writers have been declared enemies of the state, and artists are still told what is and what is not acceptable, astonished a number of students. Many reacted not only with anger but with wonder. 'What makes someone keep writing,' one girl wrote, 'even when they face imprisonment- and/or death?' They, too, began to shake their heads, as do we all, at the irony of so much great literature coming out of a land that has done so much to destroy the heart and soul of its writers." (Huidekoper 43) It is a significant reaction coming from the resident of a country which engaged in State-sponsored violence and suppression of its left-leaning artists, writers, filmmakers, actors, playwrights and thinkers in the 1940s and 50s. The witch hunts launched under McCarthyism are well documented and very well known. Reactions such as the one quoted here exhibit a prejudice and a certain degree of self-righteousness in the American attitude towards communist Russia.

However, the position from where India began its cultural exchange with Soviet Russia, which was a very valuable and powerful ally for a newly decolonised nation in formation, was very different. And since Russia remains an important ally of India, our position on Russia continues to be different. Teaching a course such as the one in question, is therefore a tight-rope walk. Considering that most of the recent and rigorous research on Russian literature available in English is taking place in the United States of America (thanks to all those university departments which started as part of the larger “Sputnik Effect”), the task of the Indian teacher teaching Russian literature in English translation becomes more complex. One has to approach cautiously the political biases and prejudice that might have crept into the study of particular 20th century Russian literary texts, especially those which present a critical perspective on the Soviet Union. In a nutshell, it may be said that the study material from west is being perused through a very conscious Indian gaze in this course.

The bigger challenge however, is to find a balance within the syllabus between various political positions. The purpose of such a course at graduate level is to introduce twentieth century Russian literature to the students in all its complexity. Therefore, one cannot restrict oneself either to Soviet literature or to its critique. The past has to be presented, without any bias, as a comprehensible whole. On one end of this past’s spectrum is avant-garde writing which was seen as extremely elite and often even aristocratic in its origins. And on the other end is Socialist literature which has its own historical importance as the documentation of a political dream which did come true to some extent. Since my attempt to place these works on syllabus is also aimed at navigating different literary responses to the revolution and its after-effects, it is imperative to maintain a balance in terms of the time and energy spent on both the responses to the revolution and the Soviet regime- the loyal, hopeful and optimist response as well the dissident, sceptical and critical one. Through this exercise, I have also tried to test the limits of Area Studies (which have their origins, steeped as they are, in the doubtful arena of Cold War) by seeking inlets into an area largely ignored by Literature departments partly due to its extreme entanglement with revolutions, turbulent political changes, ideologies, witch-hunts and state-sponsored violence. The problem posed by these entanglements is mostly methodological, as mentioned earlier. To resolve this problem, the course follows a mixed approach with following modules: The Revolution and the Socialist Order (reading Lenin and Blok), The Dissident Modernist Poet (reading Mandelstaum, Akhmatova, Tsvetaeva, Mayakovsky), Changes in the Socialist Order and The Soviet Artist (reading Gorky, Mayakovsky, Kataev, Babel and Sholokhov) and Dissent in Prose (reading Bulgakov, Bunin, Pasternak and Solzhenitsyn). By no means is this a final reading list including all the significant writers who forged an important connection with art and the State in twentieth century Russia. Yet this list manages to introduce the students to this literature in significant, if not all-encompassing detail. Some works by such authors are studied in this course for a thorough understanding of the diverse perspectives on revolution and radicalism that emerged in the first half of twentieth century. Questions related to censorship, exile, loyalty, protest and silencing of dissent are raised during class discussions. Some political speeches are also examined in order to understand the political climate of Russia under different leaders.

The larger pedagogical approach in this course is to introduce the students to the political/ideological mosaic that Russia was in the first half of twentieth century. This approach is further framed by the understanding that contemporary youth must be equipped to appreciate the nuances of political positions taken by authors and poets historically not just to portray reality but also to participate in changing/moulding it. Finally, through these approaches, a sensitization is sought towards a nation which has been a major cultural as well as political influence on modern and independent India.

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